

Entrepreneurial Orientation and Performance of Poultry Farmers in Benue State, Nigeria

Felix Paul Yiljap¹, Professor Helen Afang Andow², Dr. Esther Yimi Bagobiri³

^{1,2}Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Administration, Bingham University, Karu

³Department of Business Administration, Deputy Dean of postgraduate school, Karu

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*Corresponding author: Felix Paul Yiljap

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Abstract

Original Research Article

Poultry farming constitutes a vital segment of the agricultural sector in Benue State, Nigeria. It plays a significant role in ensuring food security, generating employment opportunities, and contributing to the state's economic diversification. The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on the performance of poultry farmers in Benue State, Nigeria. A cross-sectional research design was adopted. The population comprised 78,286 poultry farmers in Benue State, and a sample size of 458 was determined using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample formula. A structured questionnaire was adapted and administered to 458 respondents, and 449 questionnaires were returned, representing a 98% response rate. A homogeneous purposive sampling technique was used. Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was employed as the technique for data analysis. The study found that autonomy had a positive and significant effect on the performance of poultry farmers, while competitive aggressiveness had a negative but significant effect. Poultry farmers should empower farm workers with specific responsibilities and the authority to make decisions within their domains. They should also regularly monitor local market prices for poultry products (meat and eggs), feed costs, and competitor activities within Benue State and its environs.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Orientation, Autonomy, Competitive Aggressiveness, Performance of Poultry Farmers.

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INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurial orientation (EO) is not a static trait but rather a dynamic process that can be fostered and developed within organizations. It reflects a company's commitment to seeking out and exploiting new opportunities, even in the face of uncertainty. In the globalized world, businesses with strong Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) are better positioned to navigate uncertainties, exploit global value chains, and achieve sustainable growth (Anderson *et al.*, 2020). In Nigeria, EO is particularly relevant for driving economic diversification and sustainable development. The country's over-reliance on the oil sector has created vulnerabilities to global commodity price fluctuations. Promoting EO can stimulate the growth of non-oil sectors, such as manufacturing, agriculture, and technology, thereby fostering a more resilient and diversified economy (Anyagou *et al.*, 2022).

Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) played a significant role

in improving the economy of Benue State by encouraging the creation of new businesses, which in turn generate employment opportunities (Lumpkin & Dess, 2020). Autonomy is the freedom and independence to make decisions without excessive oversight, which is crucial for fostering creativity (Garcia & Lopez, 2022). Competitive aggressiveness, involving assertive actions for competitive advantage, is vital for market penetration (Adebayo & Usman, 2024). Competitive aggressiveness can be demonstrated through intense marketing and aggressive pricing strategies (Ahmed & Rahman, 2024).

Poultry farming in Benue State, Nigeria, has emerged as a significant agricultural activity, with the National Agricultural Sample Census (NASC) 2022 reporting that 65.2% of agricultural households in the State engage in poultry farming, the highest proportion in the country (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2024). However, the sector faces substantial challenges that have adversely

affected its performance and sustainability.

In 2023, poultry farmers across Nigeria reported collective losses exceeding ₦3 trillion due to escalating production costs, including a 79.23% year-on-year increase in maize prices, a primary ingredient in poultry feed (Nairametrics, 2024). This economic strain led to the closure of over 50% of poultry farms nationwide, with each state, including Benue, incurring losses estimated at ₦6 billion (The Guardian, 2024).

These challenges underscore the need for targeted interventions to enhance the productivity and sustainability of poultry farming in Benue State. Addressing issues such as rising feed costs, climate change impacts, and limited access to capital and support services is crucial for revitalizing the sector and ensuring its contribution to the state's agricultural economy. This research examined the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on the performance of poultry farmers in Benue State, Nigeria.

The following research questions were raised:

- i. To what extent does autonomy affect the performance of poultry farmers in Benue State, Nigeria?
- ii. How does competitive aggressiveness affect the performance of poultry farmers in Benue State, Nigeria?

The objective of this study is to examine the effect of entrepreneurial orientation and performance of poultry farmers in Benue State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- iii. Investigate the effect of autonomy and performance of poultry farmers in Benue state, Nigeria.
- iv. Examine the effect of competitive aggressiveness on performance of poultry farmers in Benue State, Nigeria.

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested:
 Ho₁: Autonomy has no significant effect on the performance of poultry farmers in Benue State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: Competitive aggressiveness has no significant effect on the performance of poultry farmers in Benue State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Figure 1: A Model of Conceptual Framework

Source: Adapted from Al-Mamary and Alshallaqi, (2022).

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Entrepreneurial Orientation

Entrepreneurial orientation is essential for businesses to remain competitive in a rapidly changing marketplace (Wales *et al.*, 2020). Entrepreneurial orientation (EO) refers to the overall mindset and strategic approach of an organization that emphasizes innovation, proactiveness, risk-taking, autonomy and competitive aggressiveness. These characteristics are evident in the firm's decision-making processes, practices, and behaviors. In simpler terms, EO reflects how an organization acts entrepreneurially. In essence, an entrepreneurial orientation enables poultry farmers to

adapt to changing market conditions, improve their operations, and enhance their profitability.

Entrepreneurial orientation is an ongoing activity to improve innovative capabilities, risk management, effective use of resources, and value development to retain customers and benefit the organization (Al-Mamary & Alshallaqi, 2022). This variable includes the following indicators: autonomy (the ability to make their own decisions regarding performance achievement); risk-taking (courage to take opportunities in the uncertainty of decision making) and proactiveness. This study adopted autonomy and competitive aggressiveness.

Autonomy

Autonomy is defined as the freedom to make independent decisions and control one's work, holds significant appeal for many entrepreneurs (Krueger, 2021). Exploring models that provide necessary support and resources while respecting entrepreneurial autonomy remains crucial. Autonomy refers to the freedom and independence individuals or organizations have to make their own choices and take action without excessive external control (Smith & Johnson, 2023). It encompasses the ability to set goals, make decisions, and approach tasks in a self-directed manner. Independence, as viewed through the lens of entrepreneurial orientation, principally pertains to strategic autonomy (Al-Mamary *et al.*, 2020). Autonomy refers to the state of being self-governing and having the freedom to make one's own choices without external control or coercion. It encompasses the ability to act independently, set one's own goals, and make decisions that impact oneself or a group. Autonomy refers to the extent to which farmers can make independent decisions regarding their operations.

Competitive Aggressiveness

Competitive aggressiveness refers to an individual's or organization's strong desire to outperform competitors and achieve success (Chen & Li, 2023). It involves a proactive and assertive approach to competition, but one that adheres to ethical and legal boundaries. Competitive aggressiveness should be distinguished from destructive competitiveness, which involves unethical or illegal tactics to gain an advantage. Competitive aggressiveness involves a drive to gain an advantage over others in competitive scenarios. It is often associated with a strong desire to win and a willingness to take risks to achieve victory (Stambaugh & Stambaugh, 2020). Competitive aggressiveness refers to the proactive and sustained approach a company takes to challenge and outperform its competitors in the market. It involves a calculated blend of actions aimed at gaining a competitive advantage. The competitive aggressiveness of poultry farmers refers to the extent to which they adopt proactive and assertive strategies to gain and maintain a competitive edge in the market. This involves a range of behaviors and practices, driven by the need to increase market share, profitability, and overall business success.

Performance of Poultry Farmers

Performance generally refers to the degree to which an individual, team, or organization achieves its goals or objectives (Cameron & Ramanujam, 2024). Poultry farms have specific objectives, like maximizing meat or egg production, ensuring bird health, and achieving profitability. Performance can be categorized based on different dimensions like Financial such as profitability; return on investment, revenue growth (KPMG, 2024). According to Rofiaty *et al.* (2022), performance is the extent to which the company achieves the goals that have been set. So far, most companies have focused on the resulting economic goals. It underlies the company to change its orientation to become a green

economy. The achievement of the company's business goals can be reflected in the company's performance. Healthy birds grow faster, have lower mortality rates, and produce higher quality products. Performance metrics in this area include average daily weight gain, mortality rate, **and** incidence of disease (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), 2023). Additionally, monitoring the incidence of specific diseases like coccidiosis or Newcastle disease is crucial, as these can significantly impact performance metrics like feed conversion ratio (FCR) (Fernandes *et al.*, 2021). The demand for poultry products is increasing, driven by population growth and changing dietary preferences. However, market access and price fluctuations pose challenges for farmers. The use of growth enhancers and feed additives is prevalent in Benue state, with farmers seeking to improve production yields (Udoye *et al.*, 2024).

Empirical Review

Mohammed *et al.* (2025) investigated the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on business performance of small business in Kano State Nigeria: A unique impact of risk taking, proactiveness and innovation. The study employed descriptive and inferential techniques for the data analysis. Based on the correlation matrix results, all the independent variables were positively and correlated with the dependent variable business performance. Multiple regression analysis result revealed that autonomy, proactiveness, innovativeness, with coefficients (0.853, 0.041, and 0.043) and significance level of each variable have positive and statistically significant effect on Business Performance. This implies that a 1% increase in autonomy, proactiveness, innovativeness increased business performance by 85.3%, 4.1% and 4.3% respectively. While risk-taking with coefficients and insignificance level has negative impact on business performance. This shows that a 1% decrease in risk-taking, competitiveness aggressiveness will decrease business performance by 1.1% and 1%. Therefore, the study recommends that, entrepreneurs should be encouraged to take calculated risks, rather than taking all the risks, since risk-taking does not influences business performance.

Aloulou (2023) conducted a study on the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation dimensions (behavioral dimension EOBD and attitudinal dimension EOAD) and firm performance (FP) through a sequential mediation model of innovation capability (IC) and firm resilience capability (FRC) in the Saudi context. The study employed sample data for this study were collected using a questionnaire survey from 225 randomly selected SMEs and analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling. The results revealed that there are significant relationships between EO dimensions and IC. No direct relationships were found between EO dimensions and FRC or between EOAD and FP. Therefore, IC plays a mediating role in the relationships between EO dimensions and FRC. In addition, FRC does not play a mediating role in the relationships between EO dimensions and FP. On the contrary, it plays a partial mediation between IC and FP. Little research has investigated simultaneously the effects of EO, IC, FRC and FP in the Saudi context. The study

treats SMEs as a homogenous group. However, significant heterogeneity exists among SMEs in terms of industry, size, age, and ownership structure.

Okreglicka *et al.* (2023) conducted a study exploring the mechanisms linking perceived organizational support, autonomy, risk taking, competitive aggressiveness and corporate sustainability (CS) of various SMEs in Nigeria: The mediating role of innovativeness. A survey was conducted on a group of 200 Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in 2022. A managerial approach was used in the study. The respondents used a 5-point Likert scale for the assessment of their attitudes and opinions. The relationships have been examined using Structural Equation Modeling. The findings revealed that the type of enterprise moderates the relation between perceived organizational support and corporate sustainability, and innovativeness mediates this relation. The research leverages entrepreneurial orientation theory to understand how internal factors influence innovativeness and ultimately CS. The study focused on SMEs, excluding corporations and microenterprises, limiting the generalizability of the findings to the entire business landscape.

Kuva and Cropanzano (2023) examined job autonomy and employee performance in various organization in Australia: A meta-Analysis. The study employed meta-analysis research, survey research design and 14 organizations. The study found that job autonomy has a positive and significant effect on employee performance across various job types. The study focused on average effects from meta-analysis, miss nuances of specific types of autonomy. The study used a meta-analysis, which is a statistical technique for combining data from multiple research studies to get a more robust overall picture. The study is confined to Australian organizations, limiting the generalizability of findings to other cultural and economic contexts.

Bii *et al.* (2023) investigated effect of competitive

aggressiveness on performance of Star Rated Hotels in North Rift Region, Kenya. The study relied on positivism philosophy and explanatory research design based on samples drawn from across the star rated hotels in North Rift Region. The population was 575 hotel employees. Data was collected by use of self-administered structured questionnaire and was analyzed by use of both descriptive and inferential statistics using SPSS version 25. The findings showed that competitive aggressiveness significantly affects performance of star rated hotels. Investigating competitive aggressiveness in a regional hotel market like North Rift Kenya provides valuable insights that might differ from national or global trends. Relying solely on self-reported data from hotel employees introduces potential biases and subjectivity, which can affect the accuracy of the findings.

GabrielleSwab and Johnson (2023) examined the relationship between attachment, competitiveness, and workplace aggression in Kenya: A model of aggressive intent and examination of the competitive orientation scale. The study makes use of means, standard deviations, and correlations 405 as population size and 217 as sample size. The results found that an avoidant attachment style caused by dissociative relational models promotes a preference for aggression through hyper competitiveness, while other relational models fail to predict aggressive intentions. The study provided valuable insights into the relationship between attachment, competitiveness, and aggressive intent; it falls short of examining actual aggressive behavior.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopted Dynamic Capabilities Theory as underpinning theory to explain the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and its proxies such as autonomy and competitive aggressiveness and performance of poultry farmers.

Figure 1: A Model of Theoretical Framework

Source: Researcher’s Theoretical Framework (2024)

Dynamic Capabilities (DC)

This study adopted Dynamic Capabilities Theory

proposed by Teece *et al.* in 1997. Dynamic capability is the ability of an organization to adapt rapidly to changing

situations in a business environment. Dynamic capability is “the firm’s ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external competences to address rapidly changing environments” (Teece *et al.*, 1997). The theory (DCT) explains the interplay that connects a firm’s resources and product markets to competitive advantage and organizational survival. It helps to show how organizations achieve sustainable competitive advantage and survive for many years in a business environment that is dynamic and turbulent. The theory is premised on three fundamental presumptions. The first is the capacity to sense and shape opportunities. The second is to seize opportunities while the third is to maintain competitiveness through reconfiguring the enterprise’s assets (Teece, 2007). With these presumptions, the nexus between the theory and this study can be observed. An organization that senses changes and opportunities as fast as possible and seizes such opportunities to maintain competitive advantage can be said to be strategically agile organizations. Being strategically agile makes organizations perform well and makes the survival of such kinds of organizations not to be doubted. The theory addressed the limitations of RBV by emphasizing the importance of adapting to change. Provides a framework for understanding how firms can leverage their resources for long-term success. The theory has difficulty in operationalizing the concept of dynamic capabilities. Lacks a clear explanation of how firms develop and maintain these capabilities. The theory focused primarily on internal firm processes, neglecting the role of external factors like technological advancements and political instability. The application of Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DC) is that it focuses on a firm’s ability to sense,

seize, and reconfigure resources in response to a changing environment. Entrepreneurial orientation (EO) that emphasizes opportunity seeking and market responsiveness aligns well with Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DC). A strong entrepreneurial orientation (EO) combined with dynamic capabilities can lead to sustained competitive advantage and performance.

METHODOLOGY

A cross-sectional research design and quantitative research method was adopted. This research employed the positivist philosophical thought. A research paradigm of epistemological view that bothers on knowledge gathering was employed.

The population of this study comprised 78, 286 poultry farmers in Benue State, Nigeria registered with Micro, Small, Medium, Poultry Farmers (MSMPF, 2023). The unit of analysis was at the individual poultry farmers or farming enterprises operated by entrepreneurs. This allows for understanding individual decision-making and performance at the farm level. This study adopted a homogeneous purposive sampling technique. Homogeneous purposive sample is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study. This type of sampling can be very useful in situations when you need to reach a targeted sample quickly. The sample size comprised of 382 poultry farmers using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) statistical sample formula was employed to compute the sample size at 5% (0.05) margin of error (ME) and 95% (0.95) confidence interval (CI).

$$n = \frac{X^2 \times N \times P \times (1-P)}{(ME^2 \times (N-1)) + (X^2 \times P \times (1-P))} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where: n = Sample size, X² = Chi-Square for the specified confidence level at 1 degree of freedom = 3.841 from Chi-square distribution table, N = Population size = 78,286.

P = Population proportion = 0.50 (P assumed to be 0.50 since this would provide the Maximum sample size). ME = Desired margin of error = 0.05.

$$n = \frac{3.841 \times 78,286 \times 0.5 \times (1-0.5)}{((0.05)^2 \times (78,286-1)) + (3.841 \times 0.5 \times (1-0.5))}$$

$$= 75,174.1315$$

196.67275, n = 382, Therefore, the sample size is 382 poultry farmers.

The computed sample sizes for the study therefore are 382 poultry farmers in Benue State. Accordingly, the recommended sample size was increased by 20% as

$$\left(\frac{20}{100} \times 382\right) + 382 = (0.2 \times 382) + 382 = 76 + 382 = 458 \text{ poultry farmers.}$$

This research employed primary sources of data. Primary data are the original information obtain directly from the respondents to solve the problem occurring at hand using research instrument. This study adapted structured

questionnaire from Fox *et al.* (2022) as high threshold for non-response allowance. The final sample size used for the study is seen below.

questionnaire from Al Mamun and Fazal (2018) to obtain information from respondents and the variables are measured on a five-point Likert-type scale from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree from 5 to 1 respectively.

Validity and Reliability

This study adopted composite reliability, convergent validity using Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and discriminant validity using Fornell and Lacker criterion. The criterion for assessing construct reliability using composite reliability is that the values should be higher than 0.70 (Hair *et al.*, 2022). This threshold indicates that the measures used to capture a construct are internally consistent and reliable. Results of the measurement model showed that values of composite reliability were higher than the threshold value 0.70, indicating that the construct has adequate reliability. For convergent validity, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value needs to be 0.5 or more (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Discriminant validity was assessed using the Fornell-Larcker criterion (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), which requires that the average variance extracted (AVE) for

each construct be greater than the squared correlations between that construct and all other constructs in the model.

This paper employed the Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with the aid of the SmartPLS Application Software Package version 4.1.1.1. Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) is made up of measurement model or outer model which show the relationship between constructs and their indicators such as construct reliability and validity such as composite reliability, convergent validity, discriminant validity using Fornell and Lacker Criterion and structural model described the relationship between latent variables in order to predict the expected outcome for hypothesis testing includes path coefficient using probability (p-value), coefficient of determination (R^2), Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and model fit.

Figure 2: Model Specification

Source: SmartPLS Output Version (v) 4.1.1.1

A model specification in Figure 2 showing the direct relationship between the study variables. Where: AT = Autonomy, CA = Competitive Aggressiveness and PP = Performance of Poultry Farmers

This study tested the research hypotheses by rejecting the null hypothesis (HO) when p-value < 0.05 significance level and failing to reject the null hypotheses (HO) when p-value > 0.05 significance level.

Data Analysis and Results

Table 1: Assessment of Normality

Indicators	Mean	Median	Observed min	Observed max	Standard deviation	Excess kurtosis	Skewness	Number of observations used	
AT1	4.192	4	1	5	0.825	1.127	-0.99	449	0
AT2	4.265	4	2	5	0.778	0.173	-0.842	449	0
AT4	3.842	4	1	5	0.962	-0.116	-0.582	449	0
AT5	3.987	4	1	5	0.88	-0.177	-0.583	449	0
CA1	3.842	4	1	5	1.047	0.256	-0.826	449	0
CA3	4.069	4	1	5	0.84	0.480	-0.764	449	0
CA5	4.236	4	1	5	0.864	0.892	-1.058	449	0
PP4	3.84	4	1	5	0.972	-0.072	-0.608	449	0
PP5	4.009	4	1	5	0.870	-0.247	-0.587	449	0

Source: *SmartPLS v. 4.1.1.1 Output (2025)*

For normal uni-variate distribution, the values between -2 and +2 for asymmetry and kurtosis are considered acceptable to attest normality of data (George & Mallery, 2005). From Table 1 it is evident that values for skewness

and kurtosis are in the acceptable range hence indicating that the data are normally distributed and can be used for further analysis

Table 2: Internal Consistency and Convergent Validity Report

Variables	Indicators	Factor Loadings	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Autonomy	AT1	0.727	0.870	0.628
	AT2	0.755		
	AT4	0.822		
	AT5	0.858		
	AT3	0.708		
Competitive Aggressiveness	CA1	0.784	0.838	0.634
	CA3	0.809		
	CA5	0.795		
Performance of Poultry Farmers	PP4	0.862	0.861	0.756
	PP5	0.877		

Source: *SmartPLS v. 4.1.1.1 Output (2025)* Key: AT–Autonomy; CA-

Competitive Aggressiveness,

PP- Performance of Poultry Farmers

Criteria: AT3, CA2, CA4, PP1, PP2 and PP3 were deleted because they failed on factor loadings less than

0.708 (Hair *et al.*, 2019). The result of this study showed that Composite reliability (CR) was > 0.7 and AVE was > 0.5. According to Hair *et al.* (2019), the CR values should be at least 0.7, AVE should be greater than 0.5.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity using Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Variables	1	2	3
1. Autonomy	0.792		
2. Competitive Aggressiveness	0.411	0.796	
3. Performance of Poultry Farmers	0.709	0.313	0.87

Source: *SmartPLS v. 4.1.1.1 Output (2025)*

Fornell-Larcker criteria of discriminant validity established discriminant validity among constructs at a point where the squared AVE in the diagonal in Table 3 is

greater is higher than the correlation with other constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 4: Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Variable	R-square	R-square adjusted
Performance of Poultry Farmers	0.830	0.829

Source: *SmartPLS v. 4.1.1.1 Output (2025)*

The results in Table 4 revealed that coefficient of determination (R²) value of 83.0% variance in performance of poultry farmers are explained by autonomy and competitive aggressiveness. According to Cohen (1988),

R² values of 0.02, 0.13, and 0.26 are considered weak, moderate and substantial respectively. This means the variance in performance of poultry farmers is substantial.

Table 5: Collinearity Statistics- Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Independent Variables	Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)
Autonomy	1.203
Competitive Aggressiveness	1.203

Source: *SmartPLS v. 4.1.1.1 Output (2025)*

There is no multicollinearity in the data analysis of statistics showed that this assumption has been met as, VIF scores in Table 5 were well below 3.3 (Statistics = 1.203

and 1.203) for autonomy and competitive aggressiveness respectively. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value should be ≤ 3.3 (Diamantopoulos & Siguaw, 2006).

Figure 3: Structural Model Path Analysis

Source: SmartPLS v. 4.1.1.1 Output (2025)

Factor loading show how well an item represents the underlying construct. According to Hair *et al.* (2019) indicators loading must be at least 0.708. Figure 3 showed

the retained indicators of three constructs of autonomy, competitive aggressiveness and performance of poultry farmers.

Table 6: Assessing Path Coefficient and Hypotheses Testing

Research Hypotheses	Path Relationship	$\beta(O)$	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Decision
Ho1	Autonomy -> Performance of Poultry Farmers	0.938	0.939	0.014	66.32	0.000	Reject the null Hyp.
Ho2	Competitive Aggressiveness -> Performance of Poultry Farmers	-0.072	-0.071	0.024	2.974	0.003	Reject the null Hyp.

Source: SmartPLS v. 4.1.1.1 Output (2025)

Test of Research Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

The result from the path coefficient Table 6 revealed that autonomy had a probability value (p-value) of $0.000 < 0.05$ which implies that autonomy had a significant effect on the performance of poultry farmers in Benue State, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Test of Hypothesis Two

The result from the path coefficient Table 6 showed that competitive aggressiveness had a probability value (p-value) of $0.003 < 0.05$ which implies that competitive aggressiveness had a significant effect on the performance of poultry farmers in Benue State, Nigeria. Therefore, the

null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

A bootstrapping command was carried out and the result displayed the path coefficient and the p-value in Table 6 based on the direct relationships on two-tailed tests at 95% level of significance as postulated in the hypotheses. The results showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between autonomy and performance of poultry farmers because the p-value of 0.000 was found to be less than threshold of 0.05. This study is consistent with the study conducted by Kuva and Cropanzano (2023). The study found that job autonomy has a positive and significant effect on performance of poultry farmers. This study aligns with the theory of Dynamic capability adopted by Teece *et al.* in 1997. Dynamic capability is the ability of an organization to

adapt rapidly to changing situations in a business environment. Autonomy is the highest contributor to performance of poultry farmers with Beta value of 0.938. Competitive aggressiveness revealed a negative but significant effect on performance of poultry farmers because the p-value of 0.003 was found to be less than the threshold of 0.05. This study agreed with the study conducted by Bii *et al.* (2023). The findings showed that

competitive aggressiveness significantly affects performance of star rated hotels. This study is consistent with the theory of Dynamic capability adopted by Teece *et al.* in 1997. The theory (DCT) explains the interplay that connects a firm's resources and product markets to competitive advantage and organizational survival. Competitive aggressiveness is the least contributor to performance of poultry farmers with Beta value of -0.072.

Table 7: Predictive Relevance (Q²)

Variable	Q ² predict	RMSE	MAE
Performance of Poultry Farmers	0.827	0.418	0.297

Source: SmartPLS v. 4.1.1.1 Output (2025)

The rule of thumb indicated that a cross validated redundancy or blindfolding Q² > 0.5 is regarded as a predictive model (Chin, 2010). Table 7 revealed that that

there is predictive relevance because Q² value of 0.827 for performance of poultry farming is > 0.5. A higher Q² indicates better predictive accuracy of the model.

Table 8: Model Fit

Fit Indices	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.018	0.018
d_ ULS	0.628	0.628
d_ G	0.916	0.916
Chi-square	1706.777	1706.777
NFI	0.441	0.441

Source: SmartPLS v. 4.1.1.1 Output (2025)

Table 8 showed the result of the model goodness of fit. This study used the standardized root mean square residuals (SRMR). The choice of this index was based on the fact that the SRMR provides the absolute fit measure where a value of zero indicates a perfect fit. The study adopted Hu and Bentler's (1998) suggestion that a value of less than 0.08 represents a good fit while applying SRMR for model goodness of fit. The study result indicates an SRMR value of 0.018 which is less than 0.08, therefore indicating the fitness of the model of this study as suggested by Hu and Bentler (1998); Ringle *et al.* (2019).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this study concluded that autonomy and competitive aggressiveness led to increase in performance of poultry farmers.

The following recommendations are made:

- i. Poultry farmers should empower farmworkers with specific responsibilities and the authority to make decisions within their domains.

Poultry farmers should regularly monitor local market prices for poultry products (meat and eggs), feed costs, and competitor activities within Benue State and its environs.

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